

The Dual Theorem concerning Aubert Line

Professor Ion Patrascu, National College "Buzesti Brothers" Craiova - Romania
 Professor Florentin Smarandache, University of New Mexico, Gallup, USA

In this article we introduce the concept of Bobillier transversal of a triangle with respect to a point in its plan; we prove the Aubert Theorem about the collinearity of the orthocenters in the triangles determined by the sides and the diagonals of a complete quadrilateral, and we obtain the Dual Theorem of this Theorem.

Theorem 1 (E. Bobillier)

Let ABC be a triangle and M a point in the plane of the triangle so that the perpendiculars taken in M , and MA, MB, MC respectively, intersect the sides BC, CA and AB at Am, Bm and Cm . Then the points Am, Bm and Cm are collinear.

Proof We note that $\frac{AmB}{AmC} = \frac{\text{aria}(BMAm)}{\text{aria}(CMAm)}$ (see Fig. 1).

$$\text{Area } (BMAm) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot BM \cdot MAm \cdot \sin(\widehat{BMAm}).$$

$$\text{Area } (CMAm) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot CM \cdot MAm \cdot \sin(\widehat{CMAm}).$$

Since

$$m(\widehat{CMAm}) = \frac{3\pi}{2} - m(\widehat{AMC}),$$

it explains that

$$\sin(\widehat{CMAm}) = -\cos(\widehat{AMC});$$

$$\sin(\widehat{BMAm}) = \sin\left(\widehat{AMB} - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = -\cos(\widehat{AMB}).$$

Therefore:

$$\frac{AmB}{AmC} = \frac{MB \cdot \cos(\widehat{AMB})}{MC \cdot \cos(\widehat{AMC})} \quad (1).$$

In the same way, we find that:

$$\frac{BmC}{BmA} = \frac{MC \cdot \cos(\widehat{BMC})}{MA \cdot \cos(\widehat{AMB})} \quad (2);$$

$$\frac{CmA}{CmB} = \frac{MA \cdot \cos(\widehat{AMC})}{MB \cdot \cos(\widehat{BMC})} \quad (3).$$

The relations (1), (2), (3), and the reciprocal Theorem of Menelaus lead to the collinearity of points Am, Bm, Cm .

Note Bobillier's Theorem can be obtained – by converting the duality with respect to a circle – from the theorem relative to the concurrency of the heights of a triangle.

Definition 1 It is called Bobillier transversal of a triangle ABC with respect to the point M the line containing the intersections of the perpendiculars taken in M on $AM, BM,$ and CM respectively, with sides BC, CA and AB .

Note The Bobillier transversal is not defined for any point M in the plane of the triangle ABC , for example, where M is one of the vertices or the orthocenter H of the triangle.

Definition 2 If $ABCD$ is a convex quadrilateral and E, F are the intersections of the lines AB and CD , BC and AD respectively, we say that the figure $ABCDEF$ is a complete quadrilateral. The complete quadrilateral sides are AB, BC, CD, DA , and AC, BD and EF are diagonals.

Theorem 2 (Newton-Gauss)

The diagonals' means of a complete quadrilateral are three collinear points. To prove Theorem 2, refer to [1].

Note It is called *Newton-Gauss Line* of a quadrilateral the line to which the diagonals' means of a complete quadrilateral belong.

Teorema 3 (Aubert)

If $ABCDEF$ is a complete quadrilateral, then the orthocenters H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4 of the triangles ABF, AED, BCE , and CDF respectively, are collinear points.

Proof Let A_1, B_1, F_1 be the feet of the heights of the triangle ABF and H_1 its orthocenter (see *Fig. 2*). Considering the power of the point H_1 relative to the circle circumscribed to the triangle ABF , and given the triangle orthocenter's property according to which its symmetric to the triangle sides belong to the circumscribed circle, we find that:

$$H_1A \cdot H_1A_1 = H_1B \cdot H_1B_1 = H_1F \cdot H_1F_1.$$

This relationship shows that the orthocenter H_1 has equal power with respect to the circles of diameters $[AC]$, $[BD]$, $[EF]$. As well, we establish that the orthocenters H_2, H_3, H_4 have equal powers to these circles. Since the circles of diameters $[AC]$, $[BD]$, $[EF]$ have collinear centers (belonging to the Newton-Gauss line of the $ABCDEF$ quadrilateral), it follows that the points H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4 belong to the radical axis of the circles, and they are, therefore, collinear points.

Notes

1. It is called *the Aubert Line* or the line of the complete quadrilateral's orthocenters the line to which the orthocenters H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4 belong.

2. The Aubert Line is perpendicular on the Newton-Gauss line of the quadrilateral (radical axis of two circles is perpendicular to their centers' line).

Theorem 4 (The Dual Theorem of the Theorem 3)

If $ABCD$ is a convex quadrilateral and M is a point in its plane for which there are the Bobillier transversals of triangles ABC , BCD , CDA and DAB ; thereupon these transversals are concurrent.

Proof Let us transform the configuration in *Fig. 2*, by duality with respect to a circle of center M .

By the considered duality, the lines a, b, c, d, e and f correspond to the points A, B, C, D, E, F (their polars).

It is known that polars of collinear points are concurrent lines, therefore we have: $a \cap b \cap e = \{A'\}$, $b \cap c \cap f = \{B'\}$, $c \cap d \cap e = \{C'\}$, $d \cap f \cap a = \{D'\}$, $a \cap c = \{E'\}$, $b \cap d = \{F'\}$.

Consequently, by applicable duality, the points A', B', C', D', E' and F' correspond to the straight lines AB, BC, CD, DA, AC, BD .

To the orthocenter H_1 of the triangle AED , it corresponds, by duality, its polar, which we denote $A'_1 - B'_1 - C'_1$, and which is the Bobillier transversal of the triangle $A'C'D'$ in relation to the point M . Indeed, the point C' corresponds to the line ED by duality; to the height from A of the triangle AED , also by duality, it correspond its pole, which is the point C'_1 located on $A'D'$ such that $m(\widehat{C'MC'_1}) = 90^\circ$.

To the height from E of the triangle AED , it corresponds the point $B'_1 \in A'C'$ such that $m(\widehat{D'MB'_1}) = 90^0$.

Also, to the height from D , it corresponds $A'_1 \in C'D'$ on C such that $m(\widehat{A'MA'_1}) = 90^0$. To the orthocenter H_2 of the triangle ABF , it will correspond, by applicable duality, the Bobillier transversal $A'_2 - B'_2 - C'_2$ in the triangle $A'B'D'$ relative to the point M . To the orthocenter H_3 of the triangle BCE , it will correspond the Bobillier transversal $A'_3 - B'_3 - C'_3$ in the triangle $A'B'C'$ relative to the point M , and to the orthocenter H_4 of the triangle CDF , it will correspond the transversal $A'_4 - B'_4 - C'_4$ in the triangle $C'D'B'$ relative to the point M .

The Bobillier transversals $A'_i - B'_i - C'_i$, $i = \overline{1,4}$ correspond to the collinear points H_i , $i = \overline{1,4}$.

These transversals are concurrent in the pole of the line of the orthocenters towards the considered duality.

It results that, given the quadrilateral $A'B'C'D'$, the Bobillier transversals of the triangles $A'C'D'$, $A'B'D'$, $A'B'C'$ and $C'D'B'$ relative to the point M are concurrent.

References

[1] Florentin Smarandache, Ion Patrascu: „The Geometry of Homological Triangles”. The Education Publisher Inc., Columbus, Ohio, USA – 2012.

[2] Ion Patrascu, Florentin Smarandache: „Variance on Topics of Plane Geometry”. The Education Publisher Inc., Columbus, Ohio, USA – 2013.